

D6.3: Final Dissemination Report

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This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable provides an account of all dissemination activities carried out by LoCloud during over the thirty-six months of the project.

LoCloud supports small and medium-sized institutions in making their content and metadata available within Europeana, by exploring the potential of cloud computing technologies. To achieve this, the project has developed a cloud-based technology infrastructure to enable the aggregation of local cultural content. It is also developing a number of micro-services to help reduce technical, semantic and skills barriers, and to render the content more discoverable and interoperable.

A dissemination strategy was set out at the inception of the project in the Dissemination Plan (D6.1) and which was updated in the Interim Dissemination Report (D6.2). The strategy aimed to raise awareness about the LoCloud project and its activities amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations.
- Organisations with an interest in cloud computing, applied to small and medium sized institutions, including small and medium sized cultural heritage institutions, holders of private collections, and others.
- The Research Community with an interest and involvement in cloud computing in general, and to cultural institutions in particular.
- The European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme and related projects funded by the programme.
- Users of Europeana, members of the general public, students, researchers, etc.

The objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Identify the interests of the stakeholder community, and the main channels for communication and networking activities.
- Build and extend the project contact database by clustering with other projects, participating in events, and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts.
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels, as well as traditional media.
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, briefing papers, presentation template, and other materials for use by the partners.
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events.

These objectives were pursued until the end of the project and this final dissemination report provides an account of all the dissemination and promotional activities carried out by the partners throughout the entire project duration in the tables to be found in the Annexes.

2 Dissemination activities

This section provides a review of all dissemination activities carried out during the thirty six months that the LoCloud project was active. It describes the audiences targeted for dissemination, the means and resources used to promote the project progress and their result, and the actual activities carried out to reach the identified audiences.

2.1 Involving stakeholder communities

The following stakeholders were identified as target groups in the initial dissemination plan:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
- Organisations with an interest in cloud computing applied to small and medium sized institutions, such as small and medium sized cultural heritage institutions, national and domain aggregation services, holders of private collections, Europeana, and others;
- Research communities with a general interest and involvement in cloud computing, and a particular interest as applied to cultural institutions;
- The European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme and related projects funded by the programme;
- Europeana, end users of Europeana (e.g. students, researchers, etc.).

All LoCloud partners have been actively engaged in promoting LoCloud both to their internal stakeholders and external audiences, targeting the communities of small cultural institutions, researchers, and companies working in the domain of cloud computing, specifically for small institutions. Throughout the project partners have reached out to stakeholders through presentations at national and international events, training workshops, through press releases, news on their websites, and to their networks via mailing lists and social media. The project has organised conference workshops each year and these have been well attended.

There has been a regular and mutual exchange of information between LoCloud and Europeana. In addition to face-to-face meetings between LoCloud and Europeana, LoCloud partners have participated in Europeana Annual General Meetings, in Aggregator Forums, Task Forces and in the 2015 EuropeanaTech conference, (see below).

The Europeana office maintains the Europeana pro web site (<http://pro.europeana.eu>) and disseminates information about projects, including LoCloud, to its stakeholder community through the website, a quarterly newsletter, and its news channel. The office also maintains a calendar of events informing group members about upcoming events, inviting participation in clustering activities, and disseminating information about the project's participation in international conferences and events.

LoCloud has followed the work of, and exchanged information with, Europeana Cloud¹, Europeana Creative² and Europeana Inside³. This is done mainly via the exchange of news, with occasional virtual and face-to-face meetings.

¹ <http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-cloud>

LoCloud has also exchanged news and information on the results of the project with the national, domain and thematic aggregators within the Europeana network including CARARE, Europeana Fashion, Europeana Film Gateway, Europeana Space, TEL, Athena Plus, EAGLE, Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek, Hispania, etc.

2.2 Events

Partners have participated in more than two hundred separate events giving presentations at conferences, seminars and workshops within the local heritage and professional domains, with the aim of promoting the results of the project, and advocating the contribution of content/metadata to Europeana. The project organised workshops as part of international conferences during the second and third years, the first being held during the 18th general assembly of ICOMOS in Florence in November 2014 and the second during Digital Heritage 2015 in Granada in October 2015. The final project conference was held in Amersfoort in the Netherlands in February 2016. In addition to these major project events, partners participated in workshops at the EVA conference in Jerusalem in November 2015, at TPD in Poznan in October 2015 and at the EuropeanaTech conference in Paris in February 2015. There were a large number of national workshops organised by partners for institutions in their countries, and a series of five workshops in the Balkan countries.

The Final Conference in Amersfoort provided the occasion to announce the results of the LoCloud Competition and to recognize the winners.

Below are a few highlights of events organised by LoCloud, or with a substantial project presence, during the three years of the project. A full list of events is included as Annex 1 to this report.

The LoCloud Final Conference 5th February 2016, Amersfoort

The LoCloud Final Conference (<http://www.locloud.eu/Events/LoCloud-Conference>) was hosted by RCE at their offices in Amersfoort, the Netherlands on Friday the 5th February. The programme provided an opportunity for partners to show case their content, which has been provided to Europeana, and for the technical developers to describe the services developed in the project.

² <http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-creative>

³ <http://www.europeana-inside.eu/home/index.html>

Ole Myhre Hansen opening the LoCloud Conference

After a welcome from Henk Alkemade of RCE, Ole Myhre Hansen (NRA) introduced LoCloud, explaining the goals of the project, describing the Services developed by the project and showing some examples of the content provided. An important set of services has been developed by the project for smaller cultural institutions and to ease the process of providing metadata and content to Europeana.

Henning Scholtz presented the Europeana Business Plan and described Europeana’s new Publishing Framework. The focus of Europeana is now on improving quality of data and experiences for its users. A LoCloud partner, BJC, has provided some of the highest quality open access content that is currently available on Europeana.

Nathalie Gascoin talking about the experience of the Archives Départementales de la Gironde in LoCloud

The next session provided a showcase from LoCloud with partners presenting both their content and describing how they had involved small and medium sized cultural institutions in their regions in the project. Presentations were given by:

- Belgrade City Library, Serbia - Jasmina Ninkov and Predrag Djukic
- Discovery programme, Ireland – Louise Kennedy
- Fondazione Ranieri di Sorbello Collezione– Giulia Coletti
- Hacette University, Turkey – Tolga Cakmak, Bulent Yilmaz and Ozgur Kulcu
- Gironde – Nathalie Gascoin
- Cluj County Library – Sorina Stanca
- National Archives of Norway, Joachim Fugleberg
- MECD, Spain – Maria Carrillo
- Archaeology Data Service, UK – Holly Wright

Marcel Watelet of the European Commission followed by giving a presentation on the new H2020 programme and Cultural Heritage, highlighting calls that would be of interest to the audience.

The programme focus then moved onto the technologies with presentations by Marcin Werla of PSNC on LoCloud Collections and the take-up by cultural institutions. Rymvidas Laužikas of VUFC then followed describing the Historic Place Names Service developed in LoCloud.

After lunch Richard Leeming of the BBC described the Research and Education Space initiative. RES is a partnership between the BBC, JISC and the British Universities Film Council in an initiative to improve access to public archives for use in education. RES is an open platform that includes linked open collections data from Europeana alongside data from UK institutions and the BBC itself.

Richard Leeming presenting RES

The next session provided a show-case of LoCloud services with presentations from the technical developer partners:

- Getting More out of your data – Dimitris Gavrilis, Athena RC
- Micro-services in LoCloud – AIT, Walter Koch
- Aggregating cultural heritage metadata using the MINT platform (Presented by Dimitris Gavrilis in place of Vassilis Tsouvaras).
- On the map – Runar Bergheim, AVINET, Norway.

Runar Bergheim presenting the Geocoding service

The final session presented the results of the Competition run by LoCloud during summer and autumn of 2015 (see Section 2.3.6 below). A short video provided a show-case of the competition entries including those by the winner and runner up. Henk Alkemade presented the awards to the competition winner, Mihael Muršec a secondary school student from Slovenia, and the runner-up, Bogdan Stanciu a journalist from Romania.

The conference concluded with a summing-up by Kate Fernie.

Mihael Muršec and Bogdan Stanciu with their certificates

LoCloud Workshop, EVA/MINERVA, 8 November 2015

Partners participated in a successful LoCloud Workshop at the EVA/MINERVA conference in Jerusalem on 8 November 2015 (<http://www.digitalheritage2015.org/>). The workshop showcased the technical outcomes of the project and included the following presentations:

- Overview of the LoCloud Project (Holly Wright, UoY ADS)
- Creating mappings with the MINT system (Vassilis Trouvaras, NTUA)
- MORE: using LoCloud: services in the Aggregation Workflow (Vassilis Trouvaras, NTUA)
- LoCloud Micro Services and the Digitisation Workflow (Walter Koch, AIT)
- LoCloud Collections (Holly Wright, ADS)

LoCloud Workshop, Digital Heritage 2015, 1 October 2015

A workshop showcasing the content outcomes of LoCloud was organised by UoY ADS at the international Digital Heritage Congress on 1 October, 2015, in Granada, Spain (<http://www.digitalheritage2015.org/>). The workshop programme was as follows:

Introduction

- LoCloud: Local content in the Europeana Cloud (Kate Fernie, UK)

Technology Case Study

- Geolocation LoGeo API tool (Franc Zakrajsek, Slovenia)

National and Regional Case Studies

- Magic lantern slides and 3D PDFs: Working with diverse content providers (Louise Kennedy, Ireland)
- Romanian digital collections in Europeana (Sorina Stanca, Romania)
- Dynamics and partnership with local associations involved in LoCloud: A study case with Gironde (Agnès Vatican, France)
- Czech digital collections from the archaeology and architecture domain in Europeana (Irena Blazkova, Czech Republic)
- Balkan LoCloud Experience (Jasmina Ninkov and Predrag Djukic, Serbia)
- The cultural challenge in Umbria: Local institutions growing up in the cloud (Giulia Coletti and Claudia Pazzini, Italy)

Giulia Colletti presenting the Fondazione Ranieri di Sorbello's experiences in LoCloud

LoCloud and Communities

- LoCloud Support for communities and cultural tourism (Silvia Alfreider, Norway)
- LoCloud: What's in it for me? (Henk Alkemade, The Netherlands)
- Concluding Remarks and Discussion (Holly Wright, UK)

The workshop was very well attended and it was successful in attracting interest about the project from stakeholders.

In addition to the LoCloud workshop, the project was presented by Holly Wright of the ADS in the Tag Cloud project workshop at the Digital Heritage 2015 conference. The theme of the Tag Cloud workshop was "Engaging and governing in the Cultural Heritage services" and the workshop was held on 29 September.

LoCloud Hackathon, 11 February 2015

Developers in the Lab at the Google Culture Institute during the LoCloud Hackathon.

A Hackathon was organised for LoCloud and Europeana by Athena RC at the Google Culture Institute in Paris on 11 February during the EuropeanaTech conference. The event gathered together 22 developers who worked on innovative applications for the cultural heritage sector, using Europeana data and LoCloud services including the MORE repository, enrichment services, Geolocation services, the historical place names service, the vocabulary service, and the Wikimedia application.

Developers presented their applications to an international panel of judges including Costis Dallas (Athena Research Centre), James Helmsley (Europeana), Andy Neal (Digital Heritage New Zealand), Ingrida Vosylute (University of Vilnius) and Kate Fernie (2Culture). The panel voted for the most innovative application/service presented by developers at the Hackathon.

MoRe Quality by Vangelis Banos (Greece) was the winning application.

A website was set up for the hackathon by Athena RC to provide information about the event and the services available at <http://more.locloud.eu/hackathon/>.

The Hackathon was promoted by LoCloud partners both before and after the event. The connection with the Google Culture Institute raised a lot of interest among developers in the Hackathon and in LoCloud services. Two articles, one on the event in general, and one on the winning application, were published on the LoCloud web site and in the February newsletter:

<http://www.locloud.eu/News/We-attended-the-LoCloud-Hackathon>

<http://www.locloud.eu/News/LoCloud-Hackathon-winner>

EuropeanaTech2015, 11-13 February 2015, Paris, France

The EuropeanaTech conference brings together application developers, information professionals, technology researchers and decision makers in the cultural domain. The 2015 edition of the conference (<http://pro.europeana.eu/event/europeanatech-2015>) aimed to explore technical challenges and new developments around discovery and re-use of cultural content, with a look to the future of digital cultural heritage at Europeana and internationally. There were keynote presentations from Rewired State, the Digital Public Library of America, Digital New Zealand, Trove, Google Research, the Smithsonian, “Good, Form and Spectacle” and the BBC.

Rymvidas Laužikas presented an ignite talk on the LoCloud historic place name service during the main plenary session. Runar Bergheim presented the Geocoding service during one of the parallel conference sessions on data quality. Kate Fernie presented work on the CARARE metadata schema with Valentine Charles of Europeana during a parallel session on data modeling.

A project poster was presented in the exhibition area of the conference and attracted a good level of interest amongst the developer community (see the poster in section 3.1 below). The project was well represented by partners at the conference, a mid-term plenary meeting having been held at the National Library of France on the day before the EuropeanaTech conference started.

Rymvidas Laužikas present the challenges of Historic Place Names at EuropeanaTech

ICOMOS Workshop, ICOMOS 18th General Assembly, 11 November 2014, Florence, Italy

A LoCloud workshop was organised by the Archaeology Data Service and the National Archives of Norway during the 18th General Assembly of ICOMOS in Florence.

LoCloud at the ICOMOS 18th General Assembly: Kate Fernie (2Culture Associates), Holly Wright (Archaeology Data Service) and Silvia Alfreider (National Archives of Norway).

The objectives of this workshop were to stimulate discussion and collaboration between curators, experts and stakeholders in digital libraries, cultural heritage, tourism and local communities about new ways to make holdings more widely available; and to showcase the latest developments in supporting small and medium-sized cultural institutions in making their digitised collections available online, via the Europeana portal, through the LoCloud project.

The event included the following presentations:

- Overview of the LoCloud project, and how local cultural institutions can get involved, Kate Fernie, 2Culture Associates, UK
- Overview and demonstration of LoCloud mapping tools and cloud-based services for Europeana, Dimitris Gavrilis, ATHENA Research Centre, Greece
- Overview and demonstration of LoCloud Collections: a new collection management system for small to medium sized organisations to make their collections available online, and discoverable within Europeana, Holly Wright, Archaeology Data Service, University of York, UK
- Overview and demonstration of geographic location and map based services for local heritage within LoCloud services for Europeana, Siri Slettvåg, Avinet, Norway
- Support for communities and cultural tourism, Silvia Alfreider, National Archives of Norway, Norway

The workshop raised interesting and lively discussions on the topics addressed and a number of participants showed interest in the project. The event was also useful networking exercise, being part of the ICOMOS conference, which attracted a considerable number of International participants from cultural heritage institutions.

Workshops in the Balkan countries

Zavod Jara, BGB and GKR organised a series of workshops in four Balkan countries: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Macedonia and Albania.

The programme for each workshop consisted of two main parts: a general presentation of the LoCloud project and its services; and a practical workshop on LoCloud collections - how to set up a digital library for small institutions.

The partners anticipated that about 25-30 participants, mainly from small institutions, would attend each workshop. By the end of the series a total of 121 people had participated in the workshops. The details of the workshops are shown in the table below.

Place	Date	Co-organizers	Presenters
Cetinje , National library of Montenegro "Đurađ Crnojević" Montenegro	15th April 2015	Jelena Đurović and Vjenceslava Ševaljević from National library of Montenegro "Đurađ Crnojević"	Predrag Djukić / BGB, Andreja Silić Švonja /GKR
Trebinje , Hotel Leotar, Annual Meeting of Library Association members Republic of Srpska	16th April 2015	Stojka Mjatović from Librarians Association in Republic of Srpska	Predrag Djukić / BGB, Andreja Silić Švonja /GKR
Skopje , National and University Library "Sv. Kliment Ohridski", Macedonia	7th May 2015	Viktoria Kostoska from National and University Library "Sv. Kliment Ohridski" and Ivanka Sokolova from Public Library Brothers Miladinovci in Macedonia	Breda Karun / Zavod Jara, Andreja Silić Švonja / GKR
Sarajevo , Faculty of Economics, University of Sarajevo Bosnia and Herzegovina	26th May 2015	Biserka Sabljaković from Faculty of Economics Library in Sarajevo and Nadina Grebović-Lendo from BAM Association of Informational Professionals from Libraries, Archives and Museums in Bosnia and Herzegovina	Breda Karun / Zavod Jara, Andreja Silić Švonja / GKR
Tirana , Medicine University Library, Albania	3rd June 2015	Monika Luarasi from Science Library Polytechnic University of Tirana and Lindita Papadhopulli from Medicine University Library in Tirana	Sara Vukušić / GKR, Andreja Silić Švonja / GKR

Distance learning courses

Hacettepe University, Turkey implemented the LoCloud eLearning course in their distance-learning environment between December 2015 and January 2016. To date there have been 79 participants in the course.

3 Means of dissemination

3.1 Dissemination materials

A set of promotional materials were prepared and made available for use in the first year of the project. These materials include:

- A project leaflet
- A general poster translated in all partner languages
- A technical poster produced in February 2015 for the Europeana Tech conference, providing an overview of the LoCloud services; translations are being made available
- A project fact sheet
- A LoCloud PowerPoint presentation template.

LoCloud: Beyond the Space

LoCloud Collections

- Lightweight, out-of-the box repository
- Provided as a service
- Dedicated to small memory institutions
- Simple, easy to start
- Supports multiple collections
- Supports many data formats
- Customizable interface
- Online support
- Multilingual
- Compatible with Europeana
- Highly available

MORE

The services for harvest, Ingest, Validate, Transform, Enrich and Publish takes part in MORE, which has the following features:

- Enrichment micro-services
- Multiple input sources
- Curation oriented
- REST API support
- Many formats
- Easy to use
- Flexible
- Scalable

OAI-PMH

MINT

- Provides users the ability to perform a mapping of their own metadata schemas to reference domain models (LIDO , EDM, Carare Schema)
- Follows a typical web based architecture
- Supports multiple organizations
- Compatible with Europeana

Other Services

Wikimedia

Web Service that uses a REST interface Communicates with Wikimedia commons and facilitates the exchange of information which include:

- Title
- Description
- Date
- Image (url)
- Source

LoCloud Crawler

A set of tools to automatically extract structured metadata from HTML web pages.

Enrichment Micro-services

Background Links

- Automatically links items in the collections to background information contained in DBpedia pages.
- REST service

Geo-coding

- Facilitates geocoding of existing cultural heritage data without location information that can be resolved to coordinates
- REST API support

Vocabulary Matching

- Create, manage, publish, share, re-use of Ontologies, taxonomies, Thesauri
- Multilingual vocabularies and format
- REST API support

Thesauri

- Automatically links relevant information from the metadata to relevant classes in a provided vocabulary.
- REST service

Historic Place Names

- Semi-automatic historical geo-information management functions
- Designed for aggregation and enhanced usage of digital heritage information.
- REST API support

www.locloud.eu

LoCloud is co-funded under the CIP ICT PSP programme

LoCloud technical poster

A new LoCloud Collections leaflet was produced by PSNC as marketing collateral and for distribution at the Final Conference.

LoCloud Collections leaflet

Partners have worked with 2Culture to translate promotional materials into their national languages. The technical poster, leaflets, press releases and a range of other materials have been made available in partners' languages.

All dissemination materials are available to members of the project for download from the LoCloud website.

3.2 Videos

NRA and UoY ADS developed a video about LoCloud during the first year of the project. The video provides an introduction to the project and its vision for developing cloud-based services for small and medium sized cultural institutions.

The video is available on the home page of project web site and also in YouTube at: <https://youtu.be/Vyo7Z4KClow>.

A YouTube channel⁴ was established to upload the introductory video. Two further videos have since been uploaded: a screen cast of the Geocoding service made by AVINET and a showcase of entries to the LoCloud Competition made by 2Culture Associates for the Final project conference.

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLfjUUivJWpqzqjKTOWgtQ>

Snapshot of the LoCloud introduction video

A series of training videos demonstrating the LoCloud Services were produced by PSNC and are available on the project's support portal at: http://support.locloud.eu/Training_Videos. The video's are delivered using the Interactive Scientific TV platform in Pioneer network.

3.3 Web site

The LoCloud web site (<http://www.locloud.eu/>) was launched by MDR in the first month of the project (March 2013) and is now maintained and developed by 2Culture. The site provides information about the project, and includes an intranet section for members of the project consortium.

The public area of the web site includes:

- About – the project, consortium and activities
- News – news bulletins and newsletters
- LoCloud Collections
- Resources – presentations by project partners, publications, dissemination materials, links to related projects and initiatives
- Support – links to the LoCloud support centre, providing access to documentation, learning materials, questions and answers, and help desk
- Events – events of interest to the LoCloud community
- Get involved – a section providing information for small and medium sized organisations interested in joining LoCloud
- Contacts – How to contact the LoCloud project.

The latest additions to the project website were sections for the LoCloud Competition (<http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition>) and for the Final conference.

Register Login

LoCloud

About News LoCloud Collections Resources Support Events Get Involved LoCloud Competition

LoCloud Competition

Competition Information

A big thank you to all of those of you who entered the LoCloud Competition!

The international competition invited students, curators and others to explore their local history through Europeana and share their story in the [My Local Heritage](#) competition.

The mission was to find images, texts, film and sound from the archives on www.europeana.eu and relate these to a story about a place and its people. We received many highly enjoyable entries from across Europe. An international jury consisting of Vilde Ronge, the Assistant Director at Riksarkivet/the National Archives of Norway, Milena Popova of Europeana and Kate Fernie of 2Culture Associates, chose a winner and a runner-up in the competition.

LoCloud is holding a [conference](#) in Amersfoort, the Netherlands on 5th February 2016, during which we will showcase the competition entries and award prizes to the winners.

[Read competition news](#)

[View details of the competition entry requirements](#)

And the winner is...

Maribor in the past and today

Slovenia

Mihael Muršec, a second grade high school student from Slovenia, was placed first with his video entry: Maribor in the past and today. "I've been interested on multimedia since the primary school" says Mihael Muršec. "I'm a member of the school computer club in II High school, Maribor. I directed and mounted the video that was recorded by the other members of the club: Sven Pušnik, Patrik Rek, Nejc-Filip Svenšek".

The competition section of the website provides access to all of the entries

The web site is made available in English. Partners have created pages about the project and specific activities (such as press releases and the Competition) in their national language on their own websites. See for example: <http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition/Competition-Information/In-your-country>.

Website statistics

Below are some **statistics on access** to the LoCloud web site during whole project lifetime, from 1st March 2013 to 29th February 2016.

Note: While systems are in place to prevent visits from site administrators (by IP and by website account), these systems are not 100% reliable, and may result in inflated visit counts from the UK. Google Analytics does not record visits from users with JavaScript disabled. There are no accurate figures for the percentage of users with JavaScript disabled, but is generally considered somewhere between 2% to 3%. Where easily identifiable, data for visits and referrals from crawlers and spambots have been excluded from these results.

Visits

During the last year, the number of visitors has increased by over 50% since the previous period. The total number of visitors across the whole three years stands at 14,638 with 72,816 page views in 22,711 sessions.

Analysis of the demographics shows that the UK provides the largest source of visitors (10.6%). Spain is the next largest source (10%) with Italy (6.9%), Cyprus (5.5%) and Norway (4.9%) the next largest sources of visitors to the website. The last twelve months have seen increases in the relative numbers of visitors from Spain, Serbia, Croatia and Slovenia; this probably reflects widespread dissemination about the LoCloud Competition by partners in those countries.

Visits by country to the LoCloud website

Percentage of visits by country to the LoCloud website, 01/03/2013 to 29/02/2016

Total number of countries: 141

Country	% Visits	Country	% Visits	Country	% Visits	Country	% Visits
United Kingdom	10.62%	Belgium	1.82%	Albania	0.30%	Saudi Arabia	0.08%
Spain	10.05%	Lithuania	1.62%	Japan	0.27%	Kosovo	0.08%
Italy	6.85%	Portugal	1.44%	Finland	0.26%	Malaysia	0.08%
Cyprus	5.46%	Bulgaria	1.29%	Montenegro	0.21%	South Africa	0.07%
Norway	4.94%	Denmark	1.21%	Latvia	0.20%	(not set)	0.07%
Netherlands	4.78%	Sweden	1.08%	Taiwan	0.20%	Pakistan	0.07%
Greece	4.28%	China	0.88%	Estonia	0.19%	New Zealand	0.05%
France	4.17%	Iceland	0.78%	Colombia	0.18%	Singapore	0.05%
Romania	3.63%	India	0.66%	South Korea	0.15%	Chile	0.05%
Serbia	3.23%	Canada	0.64%	Mexico	0.13%	United Arab Em.	0.05%
Germany	3.15%	Switzerland	0.53%	Argentina	0.12%	Moldova	0.04%
United States	2.78%	Bosnia&Herz.	0.51%	Luxembourg	0.12%	Thailand	0.04%
Turkey	2.66%	Slovakia	0.47%	Malta	0.11%	Bangladesh	0.04%
Croatia	2.60%	Brazil	0.46%	Nigeria	0.11%	Hong Kong	0.04%
Poland	2.55%	Israel	0.46%	Ukraine	0.10%	Iran	0.04%
Austria	2.30%	Russia	0.44%	Indonesia	0.09%	Tunisia	0.04%
Ireland	2.16%	Hungary	0.39%	Kenya	0.09%	Other	0.81%
Slovenia	1.87%	Australia	0.36%	Egypt	0.09%		
Czech Republic	1.86%	Macedonia	0.35%	Philippines	0.09%		

Source Google Analytics

Sources of traffic to the LoCloud website

The main sources of traffic to the website are from organic search on search engines (34.3%), direct traffic (27.2%) and referrals (24.5%).

Note: Channel data is not available prior to 25 July, 2013.

Referrals to the website

There have been 7,293 referrals from 485 sources over the duration of the project. Measures have to been taken to remove web crawlers from these statistics where practical. Over 20% of these have come via the social media channels (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn), around 10% via the partner websites and the remaining from a wide variety of other mainly CH-related sources.

The top 20 referrers are listed on the table below.

Referral Source	Sessions	% Total
t.co (Twitter)	675	9.26%
facebook.com	664	9.10%
culturalheritage2014.eu	369	5.06%
support.locloud.eu	289	3.96%
bjc.ro	274	3.76%
mecd.gob.es	250	3.43%
pro.europeana.eu	220	3.02%
archaeologydataservice.ac.uk	219	3.00%
linkedin.com	157	2.15%
us1.campaign-archive1.com	147	2.02%
digitalheritagelab.eu	141	1.93%
mcu.es	136	1.86%
cultureelerfgoed.nl	105	1.44%
libvar.bg	101	1.38%
moa.gov.cy	95	1.30%
digitalmeetsculture.net	94	1.29%
kf.vu.lt	82	1.12%
mint.image.ece.ntua.gr	81	1.11%
imlemesou.org	74	1.01%
bby.hacettepe.edu.tr	71	0.97%
Other	3,049	41.81%
Total	7,293	100.00%

Source: Google Analytics

Peaks in visits to the website.

The peaks in visits to the website seem to relate to the following events:

1. Promotion of the project by mailing list in Spain, July 2013.
2. Promotion of the new LoCloud video launched on March 23 2014.
3. Promotions relating to the LoCloud workshop at ICOMOS Florence (11th November 2014) attracting traffic from the UK and Italy, combined with promotions of the LoCloud country workshop held in Cyprus in the framework of EuroMed 2014 in the same month.
4. Dissemination activities relating to the press release announcing the launch of the LoCloud competition on May 13 2015.
5. September and October – further dissemination of the LoCloud competition. 2 tweets on 8th September promoting competition.
6. Announcement and promotion for LoCloud Conference during January and February 2016.

Top Content

The top content on the LoCloud website across the whole period was the home page (22.3%) followed by news (10.2%), the resources section (9.2%), Events calendar (6.6%), About page (6.4%) and the Competition pages (5.9%).

Page	Pageviews	% Total
Home	16,062	22.26%
News	7,345	10.18%
Resources	6,644	9.21%
Events	4,796	6.65%
About	4,629	6.42%
Competition	4,234	5.87%
Consortium	3,102	4.30%
Collections	1,486	2.06%
Activities	1,303	1.81%
Newsletter	1,081	1.50%
Other	21,459	29.75%
Total	72,141	100.0%

Source: Google Analytics

During the final 12 months (1st March 2015 to 1st March 2016), the LoCloud competition pages were the most viewed part of the project website after the home page. LoCloud Collections also increased its share of the traffic receiving 5.92% during this final period.

New vs. Returning Visitors

The site analytics show that over the three years 35.5% of visitors returned to the site. The remaining 64.5% of visitors did not have a Google Analytics cookie when they visited; this could mean either that they had deleted their cookies or that they were genuinely new visitors.

3.4 Social networks

Twitter: LoCloud Project
<https://twitter.com/LoCloudProject>
 Tweets: 317
 Retweets: 472
 Followers: 232
 Included on Lists: 15

LoCloud’s twitter account has increased its reach in the last 12 months, nearly doubling the number of followers and maintaining a high level of retweets.

LinkedIn
 A group has been established for LoCloud at:
<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/LoCloud-4984888>
 Members: 78
 Discussions posted: 25

Slideshare
 The account is used to share presentations project given by partners at events, reports, LoCloud deliverables and promotional materials. The presentations are embedded into the LoCloud website using the slideshare viewer. The table below shows the number of views by document type since the start of the project.

Document Type	No.	Slideshare views
Presentations	41	15,537
Documents	28	9,231
Promotional Materials	11	985
Total	80	

In total there have been **25,753 views** (of which 9,338 are embeds) since the start of the project. This is 150% increase in the number of views (over 15,000) in the last year, which is an indication of the interest in the project generated through dissemination activities during the year. The top viewed presentation with 811 views was given by Agnes Vatican during the LoCloud workshop at Digital Heritage 2015.

A **YouTube** channel was established for the project. The “LoCloud Introduction” Video, LoCloud competition showcase and a screen cast of the GeoCoding service have been uploaded.
 Views: 2,367; Subscribes: 5; Shares: 15

LoCloud Website Registrations
 Total Registrations: 162 of which Partner Registrations: 57

3.5 LoCloud Newsletter

The project newsletter has been produced twice a year. Editions were issued in August 2013, February and August 2014, February 2015 and September 2015. They are available from: <http://www.locloud.eu/News/Newsletter>.

A summary newsletter is distributed to email lists, and the full newsletter is uploaded to the project website. Notices about the newsletter are posted on social networks and email lists by project partners. Publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles sends traffic to the project website.

The latest newsletter (September 2015) was distributed to about 101 recipients, and was actively promoted through social networks.

www.locloud.eu
[View this email in your browser](#)

LoCloud Newsletter No.5 - September 2015

Welcome to the LoCloud newsletter. In this issue we are announcing the launch of a competition to encourage people to share their local history explored through Europeana and to showcase uses of LoCloud technologies. LoCloud partners are adding large numbers of items to Europeana from local collections held by museums, libraries, archives and house museums. In this issue we are showcasing a few items from these collections to hint at the riches to be explored. We hope to stimulate your interest and to encourage you to explore Europeana and share your discoveries via the **My Local History** strand of our competition.

Earlier this summer LoCloud released a series of training videos and online training courses demonstrating LoCloud technologies. We hope that you will find these resources valuable. We're looking forwards to hearing seeing examples of how LoCloud's APIs, services and applications are being used by institutions and developers via the **My LoCloud Services** strand of our competition.

This autumn and winter we will be presenting LoCloud's results at a number of international conferences culminating in the project's final event in Amersfoort on the 5th February next year. We hope to meet you at one of these events.

Kate Fernie, Project Manager

This newsletter is produced twice a year and distributed to anyone registered through the [LoCloud website](#).

- [Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Website](#)

A few highlights from LoCloud partners collections

Our project partners have also selected a few items from their collections to prompt people to explore their own local heritage. View some of their varied collections which include images of the [feast of "Kataklysmos"](#) from Cyprus, [winter sports in Slovenia](#), archives the [Gironde department](#) in France, a sample of collections from [Spanish museums](#) and more.

[View images from all partner collections](#)

Events Highlight

[Digital Heritage 2015](#)
Second edition of

3.6 The LoCloud Competition

An international competition was organised to encourage people to explore a favourite place or part of their local history through Europeana, and present their experience online in the form of web pages, a blog or video.

The details of the competition and the call for entries were published online (see <http://www.locloud.eu/News/LoCloud-Competition>). A press release was prepared, partners translated the press release into their national languages and the competition was launched in May 2015. Most partners prepared a page about the competition on their own websites in their national language to support their dissemination activities.

The deadline for entries to the competition was originally October 2015 but this was extended to November to allow more time for school students to prepare entries. A total of 37 entries were received. These were judged by an international jury consisting of Vilde Ronge, the Assistant Director at Riksarkivet/the National Archives of Norway, Milena Popova of Europeana and Kate Fernie of 2Culture Associates.

Mihael Muršec, a second grade high school student from Slovenia, was placed first with his video entry: Maribor in the past and today. One of the pictures from his team's video is shown here (left).

Bogdan Stanciu, an experienced, award-winning journalist and non-fiction author based in Cluj-Napoca in Romania, was placed second with his blog post: The

Extraordinary Adventures of Private Nestor.

Both the winner and runner-up were invited to present their entries at the LoCloud final event, which was held in Amersfoort, Netherlands on the 5th February 2016. All the thirty-seven entries are available for viewing on the LoCloud website at: <http://www.locloud.eu/LoCloud-Competition>.

3.7 Publications

Partners have published fourteen papers and a much larger number of press releases, news articles and blog posts. The papers are listed below, while a full list of press, news and social media activity is included in Annex 2.

Djukic, P., 2015, Usage of cloud technologies in libraries: example of LoCloud Project. http://www.citaliste.rs/casopis/br26/djukic_predrag.pdf. ISSN 2217-5563

Djukic, P., 2014, Има ли облака над Србијом? : дигитална Библиотека града Београда - a paper in Conference proceedings Biblionet 2014, ISBN 978-86-82275-96-1

Gavrilis, D., Ioannides, M., Theofanous, E., 2015, Cultural Heritage Content Re-Use: An Aggregator's Point of View, ISPRS Annals of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, suppl. W3 II.5

Gavrilis, D., Makri, D-M., Papachristopoulos, L., Angelis, S., Kravvaritis., K., Papatheodorou, C., and P. Constantopoulos, 2015, Measuring Quality in Metadata Repositories, pp. 56-69, in Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries, 19th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, TPDL 2015, Proceedings, Kapidakis, S., Mazurek and Werla M. (eds), Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-24592-8

Fernie, K., 2015, LoCloud: Local heritage online and in the cloud. Uncommon Culture, Volume 6, no. 2 (12) online: <http://uncommonculture.org/ojs/index.php/UC/article/view/6199>

Isaac, A., Manguinhas, H., Charles, V. and J. Stiller, (eds), 2015, Comparative evaluation of semantic elements, Report of the Europeana Task Force on Enrichment and Evaluation, <http://goo.gl/l7mlei>

Karun, B., 2014, Projekt LoCloud: Digitalna biblioteka u oblaku, BAM 2014 conference proceedings

Koch, G, Europeana-Local-Österreich, pp 252-292, in "Handbuch Kulturportale" Ed. by Euler, E., Hagedorn-Saupe, M., Maier, G., Schweibenz, W. and J.Sieglerschmidt, online: <http://www.degruyter.com/view/books/9783110405774/9783110405774-023/9783110405774-023.xml>

Laužikas, R. Vosyliūtė, I. Jaronis, J., (forthcoming), "Beyond the space: the LoCloud Historical Place Names micro-service" (submitted to CAA 2015 proceedings)

Stracke, C.M., 2014, Local content in a Europeana Cloud, p.196, LINQ 2014 Proceedings, <http://earlychange.teithe.gr/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/Paper-in-Proceedings-of-the14.pdf>

Stracke, C.M., 2015, Local content in a Europeana Cloud, p.74, LINQ 2015 Proceedings, http://www.learning-innovations.eu/sites/learning-innovations.eu/files/2014/LINQ_2014_Proceedings_final.pdf

Stanca, S., 2015, Access facil la documente digitale locale, Biblioteca: Revista de Bibliogie si Stinta Informaril, 2015, Issue 5, p131-132

Yılmaz, B., Külcü, Ö., Ünal., Y and T. Çakmak, 2014, Europeana Bulutunda Yerel İçerik: İyi Uygulama Örneği olarak LoCloud Projesi

Zakrajšek, F. J. and V. Vodeb, 2015, Re-use of Europeana metadata for Geolocation Services, 2015 Digital Heritage (Volume 2), pp 737-738, IEEE, [10.1109/DigitalHeritage.2015.7419612](http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/DigitalHeritage.2015.7419612)

4 Conclusion

Over the three years of the project all partners have actively engaged in promoting LoCloud both to their internal stakeholders and external audiences. There have been a wide variety of activities targeting staff in small and medium-sized cultural institutions, national institutions, Europeana aggregators and projects, Europeana itself, and also researchers, and developers working in the domain of cloud computing. Throughout the project partners have reached out to stakeholders through presentations at national and international events, training workshops, through press releases, news on their websites, and to their networks via mailing lists and social media.

The project organised workshops during international conferences including the 18th general assembly of ICOMOS in Florence, Digital Heritage 2015 in Granada, TPDL 2015 in Poznan and Eva Jerusalem 2015. The final project conference in Amersfoort in February 2016 provided the occasion to celebrate the project's achievements and to announce the results of the LoCloud Competition and recognize the winners.

The substantial number of dissemination activities has been accompanied by press campaigns and activity in the social media in the partners' national languages, all contributing to raising awareness of the project's progress and results. Increased awareness of LoCloud during the final year is reflected in the large increase in visitors to the project website and to our Slideshare.

"I think cloud based services and infrastructure for the heritage sector are the future.

Such services will help institutions to offer better services and more high quality content to user all over Europe. I invite you to take part in these two competitions and help us, in a creative way, to see new possibilities and make further progress."

Gunnar Urtegaard, National Archives of Norway

ANNEX 1: Participation in Events

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
National Meeting: BITKOM National E-Learning Association	Presentation by Christian M. Stracke, UDE Type of Audience: National key E-Learning providers	Potsdam, Germany	12 Apr 2013
Seminar for Postgraduate Course "Library and Information Studies, MSc", Grundlehrgang 2012/13 http://www.uni-graz.at/weiterbildung/ulg.html	'Digital preservation and EU-projects' Introduction to LoCloud, AIT	Graz, Austria	12 Apr 2013
CEN WS-LT International Meeting and Standardization Committee	Presentation by Christian M. Stracke, UDE	Brussels, Belgium	17 Apr 2013
National Conference for Archives: "Wikipedia & Archive" http://arkivmote.no/	Presentation by Gunnar Urtegaard, NRA, including a short introduction on LoCloud	Ålesund, Norway	18 Apr 2013
BiblioPublica National Conference of Librarians from Public libraries in Romania	Presentation: Importance of digitisation of local and regional content and Romanian contribution to Europeana: A new project - LoCloud.	Busteni, Romania	19 Apr 2013
Turkish Information Day Programme http://www.europeana-newspapers.eu/take-a-look-at-the-turkish-information-day-program/	Presentation by Bülent Yılmaz, Hacettepe University, at panel session.	Ankara, Turkey	3 May 2013
Cloud City http://cloudcityexpo.com/ http://cloudcityexpo.com/i-relatori/	Presentation by Giulia Coletti, FRS, "LoCloud (Local content in a Europeana cloud)": http://cloudcityexpo.files.wordpress.com/2013/05/abstract-intervento-giulia-coletti.pdf	Orvieto, Italy	4 May 2013
Conference on Private Archives and Collections http://www.arkivverket.no/arkivverket/Arkivverket/Om-oss/Aktuelt/Nyhetsarkiv/Nyhetsarkiv-2013/Privatarkivkonferanse-i-Sandefjord	Presentation by Gunnar Urtegaard, NRA, including a short introduction on LoCloud	Sandefjord, Norway	4 Jun 2013

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
TNC2013 https://tnc2013.terena.org session description: https://tnc2013.terena.org/core/session/12	Presentation by Marcin Werla, "National cloud-based data repositories as key element for the on-line presence of cultural heritage materials" video: https://tnc2013.terena.org/web/media/archive/5B	Maastricht, Netherlands	4 Jun 2013
TNC2013: Tuesday daily impression - short video	Marcin Werla in "TNC2013: Tuesday daily impression" a short video http://tv.pionier.net.pl/Default.aspx?id=2108	Maastricht, Netherlands	5 Jun 2013
Workshop on archives and Europeana - Europeana office Task force archives	Attendance by Gunnar Urtegaard, NRA,	The Hague, Netherlands	6 Jun 2013
Europeana Vlaanderen Overlegplatform http://www.faronet.be/e-documenten/europeana-vlaanderen-overlegplatform-verslagen	Presentation including introduction on LoCloud, Limburg	Gent, Belgium	7 Jun 2013
1st Stakeholder Meeting	1 st LoCloud CY Awareness event at the Ministry of Education and Culture	Nicosia, Cyprus	8 Jun 2013
Meeting of Regional Editors of the KAMRA portal	Presentation about LoCloud	Slovenia	13 Jun 2013
NPU Workshop of GIS Editors	Paper by Petr Vofík "IISPP yesterday, today and tomorrow" describing information systems of the NPU including the CARARE repository and a presentation on Europeana	Grabštejn, Czech Republic	12-14 Jun 2013
eCloud Case Studies Expert Forum	Attendance at the eCloud Expert Forum at Trinity College Dublin, Ireland, representing LoCloud project and archaeological content	Dublin, Ireland	18 Jun 2013
12th Specialised Conference on Historic Structures Analyses http://www.svornik.cz/	Paper by Zuzana Syrová on historic earthen structures including their presentation in the National Heritage Information System and Europeana	Roudnice nad Labem, Czech Republic	18-21 Jun 2013

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Seminars to Board of Management of one of Hacettepe University's Research Center (HÜTKAM)	Presentation by Yurdagül Ünal, Hacettepe University "Europeana and LoCloud"	Ankara, Turkey	21 Jun 2013
Meeting with Regional Committee (Umbria) ICOM Italia	Presentation by Giulia Coletti, Fondazione Ranieri di Sorbello, "LoCloud (Local content in a Europeana cloud)"	Perugia, Italy	25 Jul 2013
CEN WS-LT International Meeting and Standardization Committee	Speech and presentation by Christian M. Stracke, UDE	Brussels, Belgium	25 Jul 2013
Slovak Geophysical Conference http://gpi.savba.sk/GPIweb/conferences/XSGK2013/XSGK2013.php	Personal contacts and LoCloud launch press release distribution	Smolenice, Slovakia	19-21 Aug 2013
EuropeanaCloud Development Kick-off Meeting	Adam Dudczak participated in EuropeanaCloud development kickoff. Presented the idea and expectation related to LoCloud Lightweight Digital Library Framework.	Poznań, Poland	2 Sept 2013
Workshop about semantic web and Glam-institutions	Presentation	Oslo, Norway	2 Sept 2013
Conference: Innovative services in public library - supporting local communities	Short introduction on LoCloud	Albena, Slovenia	3-4 Sept 2013
National meeting with international participation	Short introduction on LoCloud	Varna, Slovenia	4 Sept 2013
"4th International Symposium on Information Management in a Changing World" (IMCW2013). http://imcw2013.bilgiyonetimi.net/	Presentation: "Local Content in a Europeana Cloud: The LoCloud Project as a Best Practice" by Bülent Yılmaz, Özgür Külcü, Yurdagül Ünal & Tolga Çakmak. Programme: http://imcw2013.bilgiyonetimi.net/documents/imcw2013_program.pdf	Limerick, Ireland	4-6 Sept 2013
National Conference of Romanian Library Association	Presentation of Europeana opportunities for all libraries in Romania http://www.abr.org.ro/article	Oradea, Romania	5 Sept 2013

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Conference on Norwegian Regional Archives http://samdokdotcom.files.wordpress.com/2013/09/gunnar_urt_egaard_2013-1009-kai-konferansen-i-balestrand.pdf	Presentation on LoCloud	Balestrand, Norway	12 Sept 2013
URLA 2013 Conference, "Information Systems, Platforms, Architectures and Technologies." http://unak2013.unak.org.tr/en/	Presentation: "Europeana Bulutunda Yerel İçerik: İyi Uygulama Örneği olarak LoCloud Projesi" by Bülent Yılmaz, Özgür Külcü, Yurdagül Ünal, Tolga Çakmak Programme: http://unak2013.unak.org.tr/en/program	İstanbul, Turkey	19-21 Sept 2013
Workshop at TPDL 2013, The International Conference on Theory and Practice	Presentation by Franc Zakrajšek, IPCH	Valetta, Malta	22-26 Sept 2013
IMI Distinguished Lecture - Institute for Media Innovation Nanyang Technological University	Distinguished invited lecture	Singapore	26 Sept 2013
International Symposium on Cultural Heritage Conservation and Youth Forum	Invited Talk	Taipei, Taiwan	28 Sept 2013
School Library Automation Seminar http://www.kv-biblio.org.rs/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=1395&Itemid=2	Presentation by Predrag Djukic, BGB http://www.slideshare.net/PredragDjukic1/lo-cloud-project-presentation-kraljevo-04102013	Kraljevo, Serbia	4 Oct 2013
International Conference on Vernacular Architecture CIAV 2013	Paper by Zuzana Syrová on historic daubed earth structures in Czech Republic including a presentation in the National Heritage Information System and Europeana	Vila Nova Cerveira, Portugal	16-20. Oct 2013
Meeting at Bulgarian National Library	Presentation regarding Digital Libraries and Europeana, including LoCloud	Sofia, Bulgaria	17 Oct 2013
6 th International Congress Science and Technology for the Safeguard of Cultural Heritage in the Mediterranean Basin	Invited Keynote Speaker (first plenary session) http://www.athenscongress.com/content/ontenuti.asp?page=Home	Athens, Greece	22 Oct 2013

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
MAB Meeting http://www.mab-italia.org/index.php/comitatati/mab-umbria/item/90-soluzioni-conservative	Presentation by Giulia Coletti, FSR, "LoCloud (Local content in a Europeaana Cloud)" http://www.locloud.eu/Resources/Presentations	Perugia, Italy	25 Oct 2013
Internal Seminar of the National Archives of Norway	Presentation on LoCloud	Hadeland, Norway	Oct 2013
Workshop on Semantic Web in the Nordic Countries	Presentation on LoCloud	Oslo, Norway	5 Nov 2013
ICT 2013	Attendance, distribution of folders, networking	Vilnius, Lithuania	5-9 Nov 2013
"Cultural Heritage and LOD"; Meeting at the Directorate for Cultural Heritage	Presentation by Gunnar Urtegaard: "Linked Open Data - the way forward" http://kulturognaturreise.files.wordpress.com/2013/11/urtegaard-gunnar-riksarkivet-og-lod-kort-om-status-og-videre-planer.pdf	Oslo, Norway	6 Nov 2013
AeLC International Conference	Keynote and presentation by Christian M. Stracke, UDE	Vienna, Austria	6-7 Nov 2013
Contemporary Library Conference - a Place for Innovative Services and e-learning	Presentation: Project LoCloud	Varna, Slovenia	8 Nov 2013
Aristotle University, Department of Informatics.	Presentation on LoCloud project outline and objectives	Thessaloniki, Greece	15 Nov 2013
CultureCloud / Brabant Cloud	Interactive participation in information session about a European heritage information Cloud (Culture Cloud, from Delving)	Hertogenbosch / Tilburg, Netherlands	18-19 Nov. 2013
DARIAH-AT Workshop „Digitale Geisteswissenschaften in Österreich: Nationale Kooperationen und europäische Perspektiven“	Attendance and member of panel discussion http://informationsmodellierung.uni-graz.at/de/aktuelles/dariah-at-workshop/	Graz, Austria	20 Nov 2013
GIS Day	Presentation by Irena Blažková on LoCloud and CARARE projects	Praha, Czech Republic	21 Nov 2013

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Digitale Bibliothek 2013 http://conference.ait.co.at/digbib2013	Poster presentation on LoCloud at the year 2013 conference. http://conference.ait.co.at/digbib/index.php/digbib2013/digbib2013/paper/view/54	Graz, Austria	22 Nov 2013
COP-Digidoc	Presentation about quality for Linked Data for a group of local support agencies in Belgium	Brussels, Belgium	28 Nov 2013
14 th Conference “Archives, Libraries, Museums in the Digital World 2013”	Presentation by Irena Blažková, Zuzana Syrová, Jiří Syrový “Information Systems of the NPU and Europeana” http://www.skipcr.cz/akce-a-projekty/	Prague, Czech Republic	27-28 Nov 2013
ETESBS International Conference	Keynote and presentation by Christian M. Stracke, UDE	Shanghai, China	28-29 Nov 2013
Europeana Network AGM 2013, Rotterdam	Attendance, distribution of folders, networking	Rotterdam, Netherlands	2 Dec 2013
Conference on Digital Born Archives	Presentation including introduction to LoCloud	Gardermoen, Norway	4. Dec 2013
National digitisation conference “Digital memory in virtual space 2013” (“Skaitmeninė atmintis virtualioje erdvėje 2013” SAVE2013) http://www.kf.vu.lt/naujienos/ivykiai/renginiai/957-konferencija-save-2013	Presentation by Ingrida Vosyliūtė: “LoCloud: Lithuanian archaeology in Eurpeana cloud” (“LoCloud: Lietuvos archeologija Europeanos debesyje”). Available at: http://www.locloud.eu/Resources/Presentations	Vilnius, Lithuania	11 Dec 2013
First meeting of Icom Italia-Umbria http://www.icom-italia.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=257:assemblea-coordinamento-umbria&catid=8&Itemid=101	Presentation by Giulia Coletti, FRS, “LoCloud (Local content in a Europeana cloud)” http://www.locloud.eu/Resources/Presentations	Assisi, Italy	17 Jan 2014
LoCloud at the Danish Europeana Network Meeting	Presentation	Copenhagen, Denmark	Jan 22 2014
Congress: Digitale Creativo: opportunità per le biblioteche	Presentation on LoCloud by Giulia Coletti, FRS http://www.locloud.eu/Resources/Presentations	Terni, Italy	24 Jan 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Various meetings	Meetings with several potential small institutions interested in using the LoCloud infrastructure (Arts Council, Archive Vestfold, Directorate for Cultural Heritage)	Oslo/Sandefjord, Norway	Jan/Feb 2014
Public debate “Стање културног наслеђа у Србији и значај дигитализације у служби заштите” in National library of Serbia http://digitalnaagenda.gov.rs/	Presentation by Predrag Djukic, BGB on the Lightweight Digital Library LoCloud Tool	Belgrade, Serbia	6 Feb 2014
eNOSCO International Conference	Keynote speech and presentation by Christian M. Stracke, UDE	Lens, France	13 Feb 2014
National Exhibition ‘100 Years of Benefiting Heritage’	Presentation of the LoCloud project by Franc Zakrajšek, Slovenia	Ljubljana, Slovenia	21 Feb 2014
2nd Stakeholder Meeting Presentation: http://www.locloud.eu/Resources/Presentations	2nd LoCloud CY Awareness event at the Ministry of Education and Culture	Nicosia, Cyprus	5 Mar 2014
UDE Summer School in Essen	Presentation by Christian M. Stracke introducing LoCloud as example for federation and harvesting of content collections of small content providers	Essen, Germany	7 Mar 2014
Avdelingsseminar – Seminar of the conservation and supervision department of NRA	Status about Locloud with 2 presentations by Gunnar Urtegaard and Silvia Alfreider	Oslo, Norway	10 Mar 2014
Meeting, Awayday Fondazione Ranieri di Sorbello	Speech of Enrico Speranza on LoCloud Project	Tuoro (Pg), Italy	14 Mar 2014
Meeting with Kamra (Slovenian portal for local cultural history) content providers	Presentation of progress of LoCloud and benefits for Slovenia	Celje, Slovenia	17 Mar 2014
Kulturni bazar 2014	IPCHS representative Franc Zakrajšek presented LoCloud project	Ljubljana	18 Mar 2014
LOD Fagdag (focus day for Linked Open Data) http://samdok.com/presentasjonar/fagdagar-o-a-2014/	Organized by Kultur-og Naturreiser, a project run by the Norwegian Arts Council, and NRA	Oslo, Norway	19 Mar 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Annual General meeting of the Archives of Norway	http://sara4/sara/Aktuelt-og-nyheter/Nyheter/Fellessamling-for-Arkivverket-Gardermoen-20.-og-21.-mars	Oslo, Norway	20-21 Mar 2014
Meeting at Town Hall of Municipality of Limassol.	Presentation by Marinos Ioannides: "The emergence of photographic Archive of Limassol Municipality in Europeana, through European Research Project LoCloud	Limassol, Cyprus	21 Mar 2014
Europeana Conference 2014 in Berlin	Presentation by Christian M. Stracke "LoCloud for Europeana: How can SMS & end users benefit from heaven?" http://www.armubi.de/tagung2014/downloads/LoCloud.pdf	Berlin, Germany	20-21 Mar 2014
Librarians Association (Knjižničarsko društvo Rijeka) http://kdr.hr/	Presentation by Andreja Silić Švonja, Rijeka City Library at the University Library Rijeka 'Digitalization and multiple choices - example of the SveVID digital library' LoCloud video presented	Rijeka, Croatia	25 Mar 2014
Student scientific conference 2014 http://www.fns.uniba.sk/?svk	Poster, personal discussions and press leaflets distribution	Bratislava, Slovakia	9 Apr 2014
Institute for Archaeology (IfA) http://www.archaeologists.net/conference2014/	Presentation by Holly Wright, ADS: 'Navigating Collaborative European Projects in Archaeology' Leaflets distributed	Glasgow, UK	9 Apr 2014
4th Festival of Croatian digitisation projects, National and University Library in Zagreb http://dfest.nsk.hr/	Presentation by Andreja Silić Švonja, GKR - SveVID digital Library and LoCloud project http://dfest.nsk.hr/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/Andreja%20Sili%C4%87%20%C5%A0vonja.pdf	Zagreb, Croatia	10 Apr 2014
E-Coop Meeting	Locloud presentation to the Culture Department and E-Coop project managers. http://www.ecoopproject.eu/	Bordeaux, France	11 Apr 2014
Europeana Day http://dfest.nsk.hr/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/Europeana-Day_programme2.pdf	Croatian Experience with Europeana: benefits and obstacles in Cooperation (Andreja Silić Švonja, Rijeka City Library	Zagreb, Croatia	11 Apr 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Europeana an open window to the European culture – an open meeting	LoCloud project http://www.libvar.bg/conferences/Europeana_15042014/LoCloud.pdf	Varna, Bulgaria	15 Apr 2014
Lecture, Università degli Stranieri, Perugia	Speech by Giulia Coletti on LoCloud Project as part of a PhD of 'Italianistica' lesson about digital libraries in the contemporary age.	Perugia, Italy	16 Apr 2014
Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/	Presentation by Michael Charno, ADS: 'ADS Resources Online'	Paris, France	22 Apr 2014
Europeana an open window to the European culture – an open meeting	LoCloud project http://www.libvar.bg/conferences/Europeana_15042014/LoCloud.pdf	Varna, Bulgaria	15 Apr 2014
EGU General assembly 2014 http://www.egu2014.eu/	Presentation, personal discussions and leaflets distribution	Vienna, Austria	27 Apr - 2 May 2014
KUAS annual meeting for the GLAM sector	Presentation of LoCloud	Copenhagen, Denmark	May 2014
3rd annual International Conference LINQ 2014 http://www.learning-innovations.eu/	LoCloud Project presentation, UDE	Rethymnon, Greece	8 May 2014
Cultural Heritage2014: From Natural and Man-Made disasters	http://chp.nsk.hr/	Zagreb, Croatia	8-10 May 2014
Two days conference from the Ministry of Education and Culture in Cyprus	ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΤΗΣ ΠΑΡΑΔΟΣΙΑΚΗΣ ΑΡΧΙΤΕΚΤΟΝΙΚΗΣ: ΜΕΘΟΔΟΛΟΓΙΑ ΚΑΙ ΑΙΣΘΗΤΙΚΕΣ ΤΑΣΕΙΣ	Lofou, Limassol, Cyprus	May 2014
Аутоматизација пословања школске библиотеке (School library automation seminar) http://www.maticnabibliotekava.org.rs/dogadjanja.htm	Predrag Djukic from BGB, presented the project to the participants of the Seminar http://www.slideshare.net/PredragDjukic1/lo-cloud-predrag-djukic-valjvo-12052014	Valjevo, Serbia	12 May 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Meeting with partners – the content providers	Presentation of the LoCloud – goals, progress and achievements.	Varna, Bulgaria	15 May 2014
BiblioPublica National Conference of Librarians from Public libraries in Romania http://www.anbpr.org.ro/index.php/conferinte	Romanian collection in Europeana (Colecții digitale românești în Europeana) http://www.bjc.ro/new/files/proiect_e-in-derulare/prezentare_conferinta_bistrita_sorina_stanca.pdf	Bistrita, Romania	15 May 2014
Cloud Computing Uptake in the Public Sector European Commission Workshop http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/cloud-computing-uptake-public-sector	Presentation by Walter Koch, AIT: 'CLOUD INITIATIVES IN VARIOUS SOCIETAL DOMAINS: culture: LoCloud', http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/document.cfm?action=display&doc_id=5532 Presentation, Leaflets distributed	Brussels, Belgium	20 May 2014
Cloud Computing Uptake in the Public Sector European Commission Workshop http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/cloud-computing-uptake-public-sector	Presentation by Walter Koch, AIT: 'CLOUD INITIATIVES IN VARIOUS SOCIETAL DOMAINS: culture: LoCloud', http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/document.cfm?action=display&doc_id=5532 Presentation, Leaflets distributed	Brussels, Belgium	20 May 2014
NPU Workshop of GIS editors	Presentation by Irena Blažková and Zuzana Syrová on LoCloud and CARARE projects "Portál Europeana, evropské projekty CARARE a LoCloud – inspirace pro informační systémy památkové péče"	Ostrava, Důl Michal, Czech Republic	21-23 May 2014
Session of Commissione Case Museo Icom Italia	Speech of Claudia Pazzini on LoCloud Project at Fondazione Pini; Session of Commissione Case Museo Icom Italia; leaflets and posters distributed.	Milan, Italy	24 May 2014
University of Macedonia	Presentation regarding LoCloud project outline and objectives in University of Macedonia, Information Management Laboratory.	Thessaloniki, Greece	5 Jun 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Biblionet 2014, annual conference of Serbian parent libraries http://www.gbns.rs/index1.html Predrag Djukic and Zlatko Ahmić from BGB, presented the project of the Conference	http://www.slideshare.net/PredragDjukic1/predrag-djukic-and-zlatko-ahmc-bgb-ima-li-oblaka-nad-srbijom	Novi Sad, Serbia	5-6 Jun 2014
National Library of Greece	Presentation regarding LoCloud project outline and objectives in the National Library of Greece IT personnel.	Athens, Greece	11 Jun 2014
Private Archives in Norway, organized by NRA	http://samdok.com/presentasjonar/fagdag-ar-o-a-2014/	Oslo, Norway	16 Jun 2014
Operational Digital Survey Committee	Presentation of LoCloud at an Operational Digital Survey Committee session (vice president in charge).	Bordeaux, France	17 Jun 2014
LOD Fagdag (focus day for Linked Open Data) organized by Kultur- og Naturreiser, a project run by the Norwegian Arts Council http://samdok.com/presentasjonar/fagdag-ar-o-a-2014/	Presentation of how LOD has been used in the Geocoding Application (part of D3.2, Geolocation Enrichment Tools)	Oslo, Norway	18 Jun 2014
Aristotle University	Presentation on LoCloud project (outline and objectives) at Aristotle University, Department of Informatics.	Thessaloniki, Greece	1 Jul 2014
Digital Heritage 2014: Digital Communities in Action http://www.york.ac.uk/digital-heritage/events/cdh2014/	Leaflets distributed	York, UK	12 Jul 2014
Fagdag Geodatabaser Focus day about Geodatabases, organised by NRA	http://arkivverket.no/arkivverket/Arkivverket/Om-oss/Fagdager-seminarer/Geodatabaser	Oslo, Norway	2 Aug 2014
CIDOC-CRM2014 Conference	http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/ Presentation on LoCloud	Dresden, Germany	6-11 Sept 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
CIDOC2014 International Committee for Documentation of ICOM http://www.cidoc2014.de	Workshop by Walter Koch, AIT: How to identify and formalize processes in the museum domain, Introductory Level, Hands on Tutorial http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/de/home/programm/workshops-und-special-sessions	Dresden, Germany	7-11 Sept 2014
“Bouguer anomaly, what kind of puzzle it is ?” workshop (attended by Martin Krajňák and René Putiška)	http://www.kaeg.sk/gravimetric-workshop/	Bratislava, Slovakia	11-12 Sept 2014
Constructing memory Conference	http://www.constructing-memory2014.org/meeting-programme	Verdun, France	15 Sept 2014
URLA 2014: International Congress on Management of Cultural Heritage and Cultural Memory Institutions	http://unak2014.unak.org.tr Attended by Tolga Çakmak and presentation about LoCloud Project	Istanbul, Turkey	17-20 Sept 2014
Europeana Projects Group Assembly	Participation and information dissemination by Walter Koch Leaflets distributed	The Hague, Netherlands	25-26 Sept 2014
Using Cloud Technologies in Libraries : national workshop	http://media.rcub.bg.ac.rs/?p=3702 (Serbia and LoCloud project, presentation by Predrag Djukic)	Belgrade, Serbia	1 Oct 2014
International Conference The reuse of digital cultural content in education, tourism and leisure: an opportunity for cultural institutions and creative industries, an investment for the future	Poster presented on LoCloud	Rome, Italy	2 Oct 2014
International Conference Geomatics in Projects	http://gis.zcu.cz/?page=geomatika-v-projektech Paper on LoCloud by Irena Blažková and Zuzana Syrová	Kosel, Republic of Macedonia	1-2 Oct 2014
Demhist Meeting	Attended by FRS. Distribution of LoCloud dissemination materials	Compiègne, France	7-10 Oct 2014
BAM (libraries, archives, museums) conference (Breda Karun)	http://www.bam.ba/index.php/bs/konferencija-bam/46-bam-konferencije/169-bam-konferencija-2014	Sarajevo, Bosnia	10-11 Oct 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
The Conference of the National Association of Public Libraries and Librarians in Romania, Biblionext	https://librarianscorner.wordpress.com/2014/09/19/biblionext/	Targu Jiu, Romania	10-13 Oct 2014
Fagdag Mobilformidling Focus day about Mobile applications, organised by the Arts Council of Norway, attended by Silvia Alfreider	https://kulturognaturreise.wordpress.com/2014/06/17/apen-fagdag-om-mobil-formidling-av-kultur-og-natur-i-norge/	Oslo, Norway	14 Oct 2014
Samdok- konferanse; Annual conference organised by NRA, including a parallell session about LoCloud; where some LoCloud services were presented; organised and attended by Gunnar Urtegaard and Silvia Alfreider	http://samdok.com/samdok-konferansen/konferanse-2014/presentasjoner-samdok2014/	Oslo, Norway	16 Oct 2014
ECIL 2014 – 2nd European Conference on Information Literacy http://ecil2014.ilconf.org	attended by Bülent Yılmaz and Tolga Çakmak, HU	Dubrovnik, Croatia	20-23 October 2014
Norlod; Conference about linked Open data in the Nordic Countries https://kulturognaturreise.wordpress.com/2014/09/03/a-sikta-mot-stjernene-lenka-og-opne-data-i-nordisk-perspektiv-nordlod/	attended by Gunnar Urtegaard	Oslo, Norway	23-24 Oct 2014
ICKM2014 - 10th International Conference on Knowledge Management http://ickm2014.bilgiyonetimi.net	attended by Bülent Yılmaz, Özgür Külcü, Yurdağül Ünal and Tolga Çakmak	Antalya, Turkey	24-26 Oct 2014
IMCW2014: 5th International Symposium on Information Management in a Changing World http://imcw2014.bilgiyonetimi.net	attended by Bülent Yılmaz, Özgür Külcü, Yurdağül Ünal and Tolga Çakmak	Antalya, Turkey	24-26 Oct 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Universities and City Research Centre Symposium http://www.vekam.org.tr/index.php?dil=tr&page=etkinlikler&state=universiteler_ve_kent_ara_stirma_merkezleri_sempozyumu	Attended by Bülent Yılmaz and Tolga Çakmak, presentation about LoCloud	Ankara, Turkey	31 Oct 2014
Europeana Network AGM 2014	Participation by Kate Fernie 2Culture, Silvia Alfreider, NRA, Breda Karun, Jara Zavod	Madrid, Spain	30-1 Oct 2014
World Conference EuroMed 2014 http://www.culturalheritage2014.eu/	Athena RC, CUT paper	Cyprus, Limassol	3-8 Nov 2014
EuroMed 2014, training workshop for cultural institutions	Athena RC, CUT	Cyprus, Limassol	4 Nov 2014
ICOMOS 2014, LoCloud workshop http://www.locloud.eu/Events/LoCloud-ICOMOS-Workshop	"LoCloud as support for communities and cultural tourism", presentations by Silvia Alfreider, Siri Slettvåg and Kate Fernie	Florence, Italy	10-14 Nov 2014
Meeting with Europe Department on European project	Meeting with Europe Department on European project	Bordeaux, France	17 Nov 2014
15th Conference Archives, Libraries, Museums in the Digital World http://www.skipcr.cz/akce-a-projekty/akce-skip/archivy-knihovny-muzea-v-digitalnim-svete	Paper on LoCloud by Irena Blažková	Prague, Czech Republic	26-27 Nov 2014
Conference Cultural Heritage: Recalibrating Relationships	Poster presented	Pisa, Italy	4-5 Dec 2014
Symposium on Cultural Heritage and Cultural Memory http://www.vekam.org.tr/index.php?dil=tr&page=etkinlikler&state=kulturel_miras_ve_kulturel_bellek_sempozyumu	Attended by Bülent Yılmaz and Tolga Çakmak, presentation about LoCloud	Ankara, Turkey	5 Dec 2014
Lecture in Master Study	Presentation by Christian M. Stracke introducing LoCloud	Krems, Austria	12 Dec 2014

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Presentation of LoCloud at Wijchen museum	Presentation, RCE	Wijchen, Netherlands	12 Jan 2015
Meeting with local libraries	Presentation of LoCloud tools	Thessaloniki, Greece	16 Jan 2015
3d ins Museum	http://virtual-archaeology.htw-berlin.de/?page_id=109	Berlin, Germany	26 Jan 2015
Meeting management team collections Wijchen	RCE meeting	Wijchen, Netherlands	28 Jan 2015
Fagdag Mobilformidling; focus day about Mobile applications, organised by Arts Council of Norway; https://kulturognaturreise.wordpress.com/2014/10/13/9-desember-brukerkrav-og-mobilformidling/	Attended by Silvia Alfreider	Oslo, Norway	28 Jan 2015
UNCTAD Workshop	Presentation by Christian M. Stracke introducing LoCloud	Geneva, Switzerland	2 Feb 2015
Digital Past 2015	Two workshop presentations on LoCloud Collections, and promotion of LoCloud at conference booth, ADS	Swansea, UK	11-12 Feb 2015
Presentation of the LoCloud project at the UBC http://ixa2.si.ehu.es/mintegixak/2015/asoroa/index.html	UPV/EHU	Donostia, Spain	17 Feb 2015
Strumenti per la pubblicazione e il riuso dei contenuti culturali a uso di istituzioni culturali e scuole	http://www.otebac.it/index.php?it/22/archivio-eventi/259/strumenti-per-la-pubblicazione-e-il-riuso-dei-contenuti-culturali-a-uso-di-istituzioni-culturali-e-scuole	Rome, Italy	19 Feb 2015
Digitale Bibliothek http://conference.ait.co.at/digbi2015	Information on the LoCloud project distributed by Walter Koch and Gerda Koch Leaflets in all conference bags	Graz, Austria	23-24 Feb 2015
Meeting with local institutions	FRS meeting with local institutions	Perugia, Italy	20 Mar 2015
LoCloud workshop	Gunnar Urtegaard, Silvia Alfreider, Ole Myhre Hansen, Joachim Fugleberg, NRA	Oslo, Norway	21 Mar 2015

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
LoCloud Workshop	Organised by BJC, presentations by PSRL and PSNC. Bulgarian Experience in Digitization Radka Kalcheva, Emilia Milkova http://www.libvar.bg/archive/prezentations/BGDigitization_StateOfArt_032015.pdf	Bucharest, Romania	25-26 Mar 2015
Master Universitario de Herencia Cultural - Hispana - Portal de acceso al patrimonio digital y agregador nacional de Europeaana	Domingo Arroyo, MECD	Madrid, Spain	25 Mar 2015
Kulturni bazar/ Bazar of Culture	Poster presentation on LoCloud project, Leaflets and posters distributed, IPCHS	Ljubljana, Slovenia	31 Mar 2015
Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) conference http://2015.caaconference.org/	Presentation of LoCloud technical poster "LoCloud: beyond the space" (Laužikas, R. and Vosyliūtė, I.) Poster session	Siena, Italy	31 Mar – 3 Apr 2015
LoCloud Collection Workshop for librarians of major Serbian libraries (National Library of Serbia, University Library "Svetozar Marković", Čačak Public Library, MIJ	Presentation, BGB	Belgrade, Serbia	3 April 2015
LoCloud Collections: Platform for online publishing local cultural heritage presented to public libraries in Primorsko-goranska County http://gkr.hr/info	Presentation: GKR	Rijeka, Croatia	9 April 2015
LoCloud workshop Cetinje, National library of Montenegro "Đurađ Crnojević", http://www.cnb.me/information	Presentations GKR, BGB	Cetinje, Montenegro	15 April 2015
LoCloud workshop Trebinje, Hotel Leotar, Annual Meeting of Library Association members, Republic of Srpska http://www.bibliotekarirs.org/strucni-skup-trebinje-16-17-april-2015-godine-program-rada/	Presentations GKR, BGB	Trebinje, Republic of Srpska	16 April 2015

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Europeana Vlaanderen Overlegplatform	Meeting of the Flemish content providers, provided update on LoCloud activities, networking, PL	Belgium	17 April 2016
LoCloud Collections: Digital library ready in 2 minutes presented at national digitisation conference by GKR	http://dfest.nsk.hr/2015/wp-content/themes/boilerplate/2015/prezentacije/Vukusic_Sara.pdf	Zagreb, Croatia	20 April 2015
Librarianship Seminars at Bilkent University: 9th Seminar: Cloud Computing and Information Management.	Attended by Tolga Çakmak, HU, and presentation about LoCloud) http://library.bilkent.edu.tr/aktivites/librarianship-seminars/bilgi-yonetimi	Ankara, Turkey	21 April 2015
Student scientific conference 2015 http://fns.uniba.sk/studium/svk/svk-2015/	Attended by Martin Krajňák, PrifUK_KAEG.	Bratislava, Slovakia	22 April 2015
The annual Conference organized by Romanian National Public Librarian Association	Leaflets and poster session, BJC	Oradea, Romania	7-8 May 2015
LoCloud workshop - Skopje, National and University Library "Sv. Kliment Ohridski", Macedonia	Presentations, GKR, Jara	Skopje, Macedonia	7 May 2015
Conference 120 Years of Research, Documentation and Presentation of Vernacular Architecture	Presentation by Zuzana Syrová, NPU https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7165b1g5IBUy1vakFuRHlzZVU/view?usp=sharing	Kolín, Czech Republic	12 -13 May 2015
LoCloud Collections: workshop for small memory institution professional on building cloud based digital libraries	LoCloud Workshop organised by BGB http://www.slideshare.net/PredragDjukic1/locloud-workshop-in-cetinje-montenegro-20150415	Cetinje, Montenegro	15th May 2015
LoCloud Collections : workshop for library professional on building cloud based digital libraries, Annual conference of Republika srpska Library Association	LoCloud Workshop organised by BGB http://www.slideshare.net/PredragDjukic1/locloud-workshop-in-trebinje-republika-srpska-20150416	Trebinje, Bosnia-Herzegovina	16th May 2015
Europeana Aggregators Forum	Discussing and exchanging information about workflow for aggregators, Limburg, 2Culture, Athena RC	Den Haag, NL	18-20 May 2015

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
LoCloud workshop - Sarajevo, Faculty of Economics, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Presentations by GKR and Jara	Sarajevo, Bosnia	26 May 2015
GIS and MIS Editors´ Meeting https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B-GMFFu9DT-pVDhLZGZZ	Presentation by Irena Blažková, NPU	Brno, Czech Republic	1-3 June 2015
LoCloud workshop Medicine University Library	Presentations by GKR	Tirana, Albania	3 June 2015
XXV scientific conference “Vision about Library future in Bulgaria”	Presentation by Radka Kalcheva, Rositsa Todorova, PSRL http://www.libvar.bg/archive/prezentations/rkalcheva-rtodorova.pdf	Stara Zagora, Bulgaria	4-5 June 2015
eCloud plenary meeting	Presentation by Kate Fernie, 2Culture	Edinburgh, UK	10-11 Jun 2015
Europeana Vlaanderen Overlegplatform	Meeting of the Flemish content providers, provided update on LoCloud activities, PL	Belgium	12 June 2016
Curso de verano Hacia bibliotecas digitales inteligentes para la docencia y la investigación	Arroyo, Domingo <u>Hispana y Europea</u>	Madrid, Spain	7 July 2015
Europeana Network Council meeting	Limburg	Amsterdam, NL	8 July 2015
Europeana Research workshop – tools and services, priorities in archaeology and the classics	LoCloud Presentation by Kate Fernie, 2Culture	London, UK	23 July 2015
LoCloud Collections training for professional staff of Museum of Yougoslav history (Muzej Istorije Jugoslavije)	Training for professional staff of Museum of Yougoslav history (Muzej Istorije Jugoslavije) by BGB	Belgrade, Serbia	7 August 2015
LoCloud Europeana Strategy Meeting	Presentation of LoCloud by NRA, 2Culture, AIT, Athena RC, PSNC	Den Haag, NL	4 Sept. 2015
LoCloud workshop	Ole Myhre Hansen, Joachim Fugleberg, NRA	Oslo, Norway	3 Sept 2015

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
TPDL 2015	Workshop: Cloud based services for Digital Libraries, Presentations and panel discussion, Athena RC, AIT, PSNC with Europeana and eExcess Paper presentations by AIT and Athena RC	Poznan, PL	14-18 Sept 2015
Digital Heritage Conference, http://www.digitalheritage2015.org/ http://www.locloud.eu/Events/LoCloud-Digital-Heritage-Workshop-2015	LoCloud workshop with presentations from, Sorina Stanca, BJC, Holly Wright, UoY-ADS, Irena Blažková, NPU, Predrag Djukic, BGB, Tolga Çakmak HU, Silvia Alfreider, NRA and Kate Fernie, 2Culture	Granada, Spain	1-2 Oct. 2015
ÜNAK 2015 Libraries in Electronic Age: From Content to Architecture http://unak2015.unak.org.tr/	Attended by Bülent Yılmaz, Özgür Külcü, Alev Ayaokur of HU who gave a presentation about LoCloud.	Ankara, Turkey	1-3 Oct 2015
European Heritage Days – Croatian Cultural Heritage in Rijeka	Conference in the Rijeka City Hall organized by City of Rijeka and Ministry of Culture	Rijeka, Croatia	6 Oct 2015
ICT 2015 https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/ict2015-innovate-connect-transform-lisbon-20-22-october-2015	PSNC exhibition stand including LoCloud collections	Lisbon, Portugal	20-22 Oct 2015
Europeana Aggregators Forum	Discussing and exchanging information about workflow for aggregators, Limburg, 2Culture, Athena RC	Den Haag	21-23 Oct 2015
e-BEYAS: Symposium on the future of institutional memories: digitization, electronic archive, electronic records management http://ebeyas.org/	Presentation about LoCloud given by Özgür Külcü and Bülent Yılmaz, HU	Ankara, Turkey	22-23 Oct. 2015
"Capitini, i nastri ritrovati", https://fondazionealdocapitini.wordpress.com/2015/10/30/capitini-nastri-ritrovati/	Speech by Gabriele De Veris, President of Fondazione Centro Studi Aldo Capitini, local partner of LoCloud.	Perugia, Italy	30 Oct 2015
Europeana Network Council meeting	Limburg	Amsterdam, NL	3 Nov 2015

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Europeana AGM	Participation by Silvia Alfreider, NRA	Amsterdam, NL	3-4 Nov 2015
EVA/MINERVA 2015	LoCloud workshop – presentations by AIT, UoY-ADS, NTUA	Jerusalem, Israel	7-10 Nov 2015
Meeting at City of Rijeka – Department of Culture	Rijeka Cultural Heritage Objects on SVEVID (Principa at Tarsatica)	Rijeka, Croatia	10 Nov 2015
XVII Jornada de Gestión de la Información http://www.sedic.es/xvii_jornada_sgestion/	Round Table: Reutilización de la información. Un proyecto práctico Europeana	Madrid, Spain	12 Nov 2015
Samdok Konferanse 2015 - LoCloud Workshop http://samdok.com/samdok-konferansen/samdok-konferansen-2015/presentasjoner-samdok-konferansen-2015/	LoCloud workshop, NRA	Gardermoen, Norway	11-12 Nov 2015
Seminar at Dipartimento di Lettere - UNIPG	Seminar "Il patrimonio culturale locale ai tempi del Cloud. Nuove tecnologie digitali per accrescere i contenuti di Europeana" by Giulia Coletti, FRS	Perugia, Italy	24 Nov 2015
Presentation at museum Wijchen http://www.museumwijchen.nl/	Presentation of LoCloud by RCE	Wijchen, NL	1 Dec 2015
16th Conference Archives, Libraries, Museums in the Digital World	Presentation Zuzana Syrová, NPU http://www.skipcr.cz/akce-a-projekty/	Prague, Czech Republic	2-3 Dec 2015
DARIAH Workshop Biodiversity and linguistic diversity: Linked Open Data 4 Living Organisms	Presentation of LoCloud Microservices, AIT http://www.ait.co.at/images/EU_OP-LC_151203_Koch-v01.pdf	Vienna, Austria	3 Dec 2015
International conference Services Tailored For 21st Century Library Clients : use of information-communication technologies in libraries	"Belgrade City Library from LoCloud to vCard" http://1drv.ms/1NTbQb4	Belgrade, Serbia	10-11 Dec 2015

Name, URL (if available)	Description, URL of presentation delivered	Location	Date
Sustainability of Ankara's Natural and Cultural Heritage: Experiences and Recommendations	Attended by Bülent Yılmaz and Tolga Çakmak who presented LoCloud and Europeana http://vekam.org.tr/index.php?dil=tr&page=etkinlikler&state=ankara_dogal_mirasinin_surdurulebilirligi_denyimler_ve_oneriler	Ankara, Turkey	08 Jan 2016
Presentation at museum Wijchen	RCE	Wijchen, NL	12 Jan 2016
Europeana Vlaanderen Overlegplatform	Meeting of the Flemish content providers, provided update on LoCloud activities, networking , Limburg	Belgium	13 Jan 2016
Meeting LoCloud tools management Museum Wijchen	RCE	Wijchen, NL	28 Jan 2016
Annual staff meeting, PSRL	LoCloud presentation	Varna, Bulgaria	28 Jan 2016
LoCloud Final Conference http://www.locloud.eu/Events/LoCloud-Conference	Presentations from various LoCloud partners, organisers: NRA, 2Culture and RCE	Amersfoort, NL	05 Feb 2016
Europeana Network Council meeting	Limburg	Amstredam	22 Feb 2016
LoCloud workshop	Presentation by Maria José Teixeira, FMNF	Entroncamento, Portugal	26 Feb 2016
Digitale Bibliothek 2016	Presentation of LoCloud Microservices, http://conference.ait.co.at/digbib/index.php/digbib2016/digbib2016/paper/view/113	Graz, Austria	25-26 Feb 2016
TPDL 2016	Comparative evaluation of semantic enrichments, paper submitted by Antoine Isaac, Aitor Soroa, Simon Rainer, Vladimir Alexiev, Juliane Stiller, Hugo Manguinhas, Nuno Freire, Valentine Charles	Hanover, Germany	05-09 Sep. 2016

ANNEX 2: Publications and media activity

Djukic, P., 2015, Usage of cloud technologies in libraries: example of LoCloud Project. http://www.citaliste.rs/casopis/br26/djukic_predrag.pdf. ISSN 2217-5563

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Gavrilis, D., Ioannides, M., Theofanous, E., 2015, Cultural Heritage Content Re-Use: An Aggregator's Point of View, ISPRS Annals of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, suppl. W3 II.5

Gavrilis, D., Makri, D-M., Papachristopoulos, L., Angelis, S., Kravvaritis., K., Papatheodorou, C., and P. Constantopoulos, 2015, Measuring Quality in Metadata Repositories, pp. 56-69, in Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries, 19th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, TPD L 2015, Proceedings, Kapidakis, S., Mazurek and Werla M. (eds), Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-24592-8

Fernie, K., 2015, LoCloud: Local heritage online and in the cloud. Uncommon Culture, Volume 6, no. 2 (12) online: <http://uncommonculture.org/ojs/index.php/UC/article/view/6199>

Isaac, A., Manguinhas, H., Charles, V. and J. Stiller, (eds), 2015, Comparative evaluation of semantic elements, Report of the Europeana Task Force on Enrichment and Evaluation, <http://goo.gl/l7mlei>

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Blogs

Title, URL	Authors	Date
Europeana pro blog http://pro.europeana.eu/pro-blog/-/blogs/local-cultural-heritage-in-the-cloud	Kristine Hoff Meyer	20 Dec 2013
"Om LoCloud"; (about LoCloud) http://samdok.com/nytt-fra-prosjektene/locloud/	Silvia Alfreider, NRA	Continuous
"Geocoding" http://samdok.com/2014/09/10/geocoding/	Silvia Alfreider, NRA	10/09/2014
"En løsning som kan gi mer mangfoldig innhold på nettet?" http://samdok.com/2014/09/05/	Silvia Alfreider, NRA	05/09/2014
About LoCloud collections http://samdok.com/2014/09/05/	Silvia Alfreider, NRA	05/09/2014
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Presentation of LoCloud Project on librarians blog - http://odknjigedoduse.wordpress.com/2014/10/02/	BGB	Oct 2014
All Three of our European Projects are in Full Swing! http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/blog/2015/04/all-three-of-our-european-projects-are-in-full-swing/	ADS	1 Apr 2015
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Part of the digitized archive of Agios Athanasios Municipality in EUROPEANA, the European Digital Library http://lemesos-blog.com/2015/01/05/europeana/	Lemosos blog	05 Jan 2015
Blogpost about LoCloud's technical Poster and newsletter http://samdok.com/2015/02/27/	Silvia Alfreider, NRA	Feb 2015
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Show your creativity and promote local heritage at the international LoCloud competition GKR http://gkr.hr/Lab/Citaonica/LoCloud-nagraduje-Pokazi-kreativnost-i-promoviraj-lokalnu-bastinu-na-medunarodnom-natjecaju	GKR	10 June 2015
Enriching Europeana: new EuropeanaTech Task Force report. http://pro.europeana.eu/blogpost/enriching-europeana-new-europeanatech-task-force-report	Aitor Soroa, UPV/EHU	Oct 2015

Press, news and TV

Press releases

Title, URL	Authors	Date	Place - City, Country (if applicable)	Type
Press release on the participation of the National Heritage Institute in LoCloud http://www.npu.cz/news/11944-n/	Irena Blažková	8 Apr 2013	Czech republic	Press release
"LoCloud Best Practice Network" In "AIB Notizie 2013, (2): http://www.aib.it/publicazioni-aib/aib-notizie/2013/34014-locloud/	Giulia Coletti	Apr 2013	Perugia, Italy	Press release
Press release on the LoCloud Content Provider Workshop in York: http://www.npu.cz/news/12925-n/	Irena Blažková	19 Sept 2013	Czech republic	Press release
Press release on HPN microservice (in Lithuanian) http://www.kf.vu.lt/naujienos/mokslas/1561-kf-mokslininkai-baige-istoriniu-vietovardziu-informacijos-valdymo-projekta	VUKF	15 Feb 2015	Online	Press release
"První výsledky evropského projektu spolupráce při zpřístupňování dat kulturních institucí LoCloud" http://www.npu.cz/news/16300-n/	Irena Blažková	8 April 2015	Online	Press release

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"SOVAMM nad mraky" https://sovamm.wordpress.com/2015/04/16/sovamm-nad-mraky/	Zuzana Syrová	16 April 2015	Online	Press release
"Digitální dokumentace českých památek v portálu Europeana – výsledky mezinárodní spolupráce NPÚ" http://www.npu.cz/news/16424-n/	Irena Blažková	28 April 2015	Online	Press release
http://www.mecd.gob.es/prensa-mecd/actualidad/2015/05/20150520-locloud.html	MECD	20 May 2015	Online	Press release – LoCloud competition
LoCloud competition http://www.npu.cz/news/16585-n/	Irena Blažková	28 May 2015	Online	Press release
"Workshop projektu LoCloud na konferenci Digital Heritage v Granadě " http://www.npu.cz/news/17304-n/	Irena Blažková	14 October 2015	Online	Press release

In the press – newspapers, news articles

Title, URL	Authors	Date	Type
http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/newsletter/issue25 http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/ADSONline25Europeanprojects	Holly Wright UK	11 Mar 2013	Article in ADS newsletter (hardcopy, website, and email versions).
Biblioteka grada Beograda učestvuje u projektu "LoCloud" http://www.glas-javnosti.rs/aktuelne-vesti/2013-03-28/biblioteka-grada-beograda-ucestvuje-u-projektu-locloud	GBG Serbia	28 Mar 2013	Article in the newspaper "Glas javnosti",
Lokalne vsebine v oblaku Europeane. Knjižničarske novice 3-4 letnik, 23 (2013) http://www.nuk.uni-lj.si/	Breda Karun Ljubljana	Mar/Apr 2013	News article
Article published in Portodosmuseus (professional blog with 900,000 viewers) http://www.pportodosmuseus.pt/2013/06/11/	Maria José Teixeira Porto, Portugal	Jun 2013	News

Title, URL	Authors	Date	Type
Article published on the Portuguese Association for Librarians and Archivist webpage http://www.bad.pt/noticia/2013/06/21/ /	Teixeira, Maria José Porto, Portugal	Jun 2013	Article
Ankara tarihini öğrenecek	Emre Üre Ankara, Turkey	23 Jun 2013	Newspaper
Bulut Bilişim Tabanlı İyi Uygulamalar: LoCloud Projesi Başladı Cumhuriyet Bilim ve Teknoloji,	Bülent Yılmaz Ankara, Turkey	21 Jun 2013	Newsletter article
Kroz novi EU projekt LoCloud donosimo lokalnu bastinu u "oblak" Europeane (New EU project Lo Cloud brings local heritage into Europeana cloud) http://gkr.hr/Magazin/Najave/	Silic Švonja, A. Rijeka, Croatia	15 Nov 2013	Article in GKR online magazine
News from the Ixa group in the University of the Basque Country http://www.ehu.es/ehusfera/ixa/	UPV/EHU Spain	2013	News
http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/enews/2.html http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/blog/2013/12/locloud-picking-up-steam/	'LoCloud Picking Up Steam!' a project update article advertised in ADS e-newsletter	16 Dec 2013	e-newsletter
Article about HPN microservice "Beyond the space: the LoCloud Historical Place Names micro-service"	Laužikas, R. and Vosyliūtė, I., VUKF	Aug 2014	Article LoCloud Newsletter No. 3
http://www.agiosathanasios.org.cy//Efimerida-8-2014.pdf	Municipality of Agios Athanasios news paper, Limassol, Cyprus	Aug 2014	Newspaper
Varna in Europeana https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y6O7ZSPm_2Q#t=1856	Bulgarian National Television, Channel 2	22 Oct 2014	TV news interview
EuroMED2014 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o1yIRfnBW10	State Channel (CyBC1), Cyprus	03 Nov 2014	State Channel (CyBC1) news
International Conference on Digitization of Cultural Heritage in Cyprus http://www.cut.ac.cy/news/article/?contentId=122885	CUT Limassol	14 Nov 2014	News article

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International Conference on Digitization of Cultural Heritage in Cyprus http://www.stockwatch.com.cy/nqcontent.cfm?a_name=news_view&ann_id=210358	Stockwatch Cyprus	14 Nov 2014	Article in stockwatch.com
CUT: International Conference on Digitization of Cultural Heritage in Cyprus	Paideia-news Cyprus	14 Nov 2014	Article in Paideia- news Blog
Digitizing the Cultural Heritage of Cyprus http://www.google.com/ucy.ac.cy-dailypress	Philenews Cyprus	21 Nov 2014	Article in Fileleftheros newspaper
Cyprus postal services: digitizing Cypriot stamps http://www.sigmalive.com/news/scitech/technology/185425/	Sigmalive Cyprus	01 Dec 2014	Article in Sigmalive news webpage
Our Metropolis participated in the World Conference EuroMed 2014 http://www.imlemesou.org/	Holy metropolis Limassol, Cyprus	09 Dec 2014	Article in Holy metropolis of Limassol webpage
The photographic album of Agios Athanasios Municipality in EUROPEANA http://www.philenews.com/	Philenews Limassol, Cyprus	31 Dec 2014	Article in Fileleftheros newspaper
Announcement of national workshop on using cloud technologies in libraries - http://www.fondacijanb.rs/cms/view.php?id=1007 and https://www.nb.rs/events/event.php?id=26550	BGB	Sept 2014	News
Open Education Europa - http://openeducationeuropa.eu	UDE		News posts
"Quality in Learning, Education, and Training" on Scoop.it - http://www.scoop.it/t/competence-development	UDE		Articles and news from the LoCloud
The photographic album of Agios Athanasios Municipality in EUROPEANA http://www.philenews.com/	Philenews Limassol, Cyprus	31 Dec 2014	Article in Fileleftheros newspaper
Archiving and promotion the photo album of Agios Athanasios Municipality into the European digital library EUROPEANA http://www.elemesos.com/index.php/	Elemesos blog Limassol, Cyprus	02 Jan 2015	Article

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The programme "Under the same Sky" of the State Channel (CyBC1), documenting the LoCloud - Cyprus University of Technology (CUT) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TAYHrF3y4II	State Channel (CyBC2) Cyprus	04 Feb 2015	Programme "Under the same Sky", State Channel (CyBC2)
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Easy use and creation of vocabularies: the LoCloud vocabulary microservice http://www.locloud.eu/News/	Koch, G. and Koch, W.	Feb 2015	Newsletter article LoCloud newsletter
Cypriot Diaspora online, http://cyprus-mail.com/2015/01/18/the-cypriot-diaspora-online/	Alexia Evripidou Cyprus	18 Jan 2015	Article in Sunday Mail
GKR in LoCloud project	Andreja Silić Švonja	April 2015	newsletter
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Announcement of LoCloud Cultural heritage competition in the Librarianship Newsletter Knjižničarske novice, http://www.nuk.uni-lj.si/knjiznicarskenovice/	Breda Karun	May 2015	News
<i>Iniziativa del progetto Europeo LoCloud: LoCloud Competition</i> www.fondazioneranieri.org http://www.fondazioneranieri.org/2015/07/6216/	FRS	May 2015	Online news magazine
National promotion of LoCloud competition: http://www.kf.vu.lt/naujienos/bendrai/1943-projekto-locloud-konkursas-skaitmeninio-paveldo-tema	Laužikas, R.	May 2015	News on VUKF website
LoCloud Competiton Announcment http://bgb.rs/index.php/2-uncategorised/756-n-i-drugi-cu-u-z-v-sh-r	BGB	May 2015	News
GKR info LoCloud dissemination in the Balkans Region	Andreja Silić Švonja	May 2015	newsletter
GKR info SVeVID (https://svevid.locloudhosting.net) published in cloud	Andreja Silić Švonja	May 2015	newsletter

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LoCloud competition announcement http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/enews/8.html	ADS	1 Jun 2015	eNewsletter
Join cultural heritage digitization competition Netokracija http://www.netokracija.com/europeana-locloud-104397	GKR	11 Jun 2015	Portal article
Apply to LoCloud competition Teklič - magazine http://www.teklic.hr/kulturodrom/ukljucite-se-u-locloud-natjecanje/	GKR	20 Jun 2015	Magazine
Digital technology use in local cultural heritage presentation Novi list newspaper	GKR	27 June 2015	Newspaper article
LoCloud competition announcement: http://www.libvar.bg/projects/locloud/LoCloud_competition.html	PSRL	Aug 2015	News on PSRL website
Bulgarian Library Association web site http://www.lib.bg/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=1015&Itemid=93	PSRL	Aug 2015	News article
Anabad. Noticias de Anabad. 2015-08-20: http://anabad.es/noticias-anabad/26-general?start=40	MECD	20 Aug 2015	News post
LoCloud Competiton Announcment – extended http://bgb.rs/index.php/component/content/article/2-uncategorised/779-pr-duz-n-r-z-pri-vu-r-d-v-n-n-urs-pr-locloud	BGB	Sep 2015	News
Belgrade City Library Collections available via Europeana http://bgb.rs/index.php/component/content/article/2-uncategorised/837-digi-ln-l-ci-bgb-u-ur-p-ni	BGB	2015	News
Diario Crónica. Convocado el concurso europeo LoCloud: http://www.diariocronica.es/2015/05/convocado-el-concurso-europeo-locloud.html	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
Diario Digital de Asturias. Convocado el concurso europeo LoCloud: http://diariodigitaldeasturias.com/sociedad/buenas-practicas/56466-convocado-el-concurso-europeo-locloud.html	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News

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<p>El Economista. Convocado el concurso LoCloud, que fomenta el desarrollo de servicios culturales en la nube:</p> <p>http://cc.bingj.com/cache.aspx?q=concurso+locloud+2015&d=4602140562623003&mk=es-ES&setlang=es-ES&w=ZLXBshfenp4sz5ax58tb4jCh4nNnn6tu</p>	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
<p>Europa Press. Convocado el concurso LoCloud, que fomenta el desarrollo de servicios culturales en la nube:</p> <p>http://www.europapress.es/cultura/noticia-convocado-concurso-locloud-fomenta-desarrollo-servicios-culturales-nube-20150520175238.html</p>	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
<p>Facultad de Bellas Artes. Cuenca (Spain). 'LoCloud', concurso internacional centrado en el patrimonio y la cultura locales [blog]:</p> <p>http://bellasartes.uclm.es/wp-index.php/becas-convocatorias-concursos/locloud-concurso-internacional-centrado-en-el-patrimonio-y-la-cultura-locales/</p>	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
<p>Gobierno de Canarias, Consejería de Educación y Universidades. ¡Participe en el concurso internacional de LoCloud para difundir la historia local!:</p> <p>http://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/educacion/web/estudiantes/concursos_educativos/concurso-locloud.html</p>	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
<p>Gobierno de España, Ministerio de Presidencia. Convocado concurso europeo LoCloud:</p> <p>http://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/serviciosdepreensa/notasprensa/mecd/Paginas/2015/200515concurso.aspx</p>	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News

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IES Ofra. (Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Spain) <i>Concurso internacional de LoCloud para difundir la historia local</i> [blog: http://iesguimar.blogspot.com.es/2015/06/concurso-internacional-de-locloud-para.html	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
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La Vanguardia (Culture Section). <i>Nace el concurso LoCloud para fomentar fondo digital de plataforma Europea</i> .: http://www.lavanguardia.com/cultura/20150520/54431361440/nace-el-concurso-locloud-para-fomentar-fondo-digital-de-plataforma-europeana.html	MECD	09 Sep 2015	News
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Pikabit, digitization of Crikvenica postcards: City Library in the elite of Europeana Novi list newspaper	GKR	14 th Nov 2015	Newsletter article
Article about LoCloud	Silvia Alfreider, NRA	26 Nov 2015	Internal newsletter
Croatian students who applied to LoCloud Competition http://gkr.hr/Lab/Predstavljamo/This-is-my-Cultural-Heritage-Old-Postcards-Framework-Printed-by-3D-Printer-and-Inspired-by-Europeana2	Filip Cvitić, Nikola Ugarković	27 Nov 2015	GKR Magazine article

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LoCloud conference http://slks.dk/presse-nyt/kulturarv/2015/deltag-i-konkurrencen-min-lokale-kulturarv/	KUAS	25 Feb 2015	News article
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Locloud.eu. Winners of LoCloud's My Local Heritage competition.: http://www.locloud.eu/News/Winners-of-LoCloud-s-My-Local-Heritage-competition	MECD	09 Mar 2016	News
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Social media

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https://www.facebook.com/pages/Digital-Heritage-Research-Lab-at-CUT/535809553212822?ref=aymt_homepage_panel	DHR Lab Facebook		Facebook
Posts at FMNF's Facebook	Teixeira, Maria José	Regular	Facebook
Regular retweets of LoCloud	ADS	Regular	Twitter
LoCloud Newsletter	ADS	9 Aug 2014	Facebook and Twitter
LoCloud Video distributed	ADS	25 Mar 2014	Facebook and Twitter
LoCloud new deliverables	ADS	4 Mar 2014	Facebook, Twitter
http://twitter.com/vbanos	Future Library		Twitter
"Quality in Learning, Education and Training" (QLET) Facebook Account https://www.facebook.com/Q4LET	UDE	2014	Facebook
"Quality in Learning, Education and Training" (QLET) Twitter Account - @Q4LET	UDE	2014	Twitter
Announcements about LoCloud events on ADS facebook page, https://www.facebook.com/archaeology.data.service	ADS	Regular	Facebook
Announcements about LoCloud events on ADS twitter accounts, https://twitter.com/ADS_Chatter , https://twitter.com/ADS_Update	ADS	Regular	Twitter
https://twitter.com/MagazinGKR/status/608923212878082048 Twitter (one of many) Competition – occupation for incoming summer	GKR	Regular	Twitter
Emails and contacts with heads of librarian institutions in Spanish regions	MECD	15-18 June 2015	Mailing

Title, URL	Authors	Date	Type
<p>https://goo.gl/FG9Qxx (Dissemination in IWETEL list)</p> <p>https://goo.gl/6TYtbe (Dissemination in PUBLICAS list)</p> <p>Dissemination in some other REDIRIS distribution lists</p>	MECD	18 & 26 June 2015	Listserv
<p>https://www.facebook.com/hispana.roai (Facebook of Hispana - Spanish national aggregator to Europeana)</p>	MECD	08 July 2015	Facebook
<p>https://twitter.com/Hispana_roai (Twitter Hispana)</p>	MECD	08 July 2015	Twitter
<p>Competition announcement disseminated through intranet</p>	RCE	14 July 2015	Mailing
<p>Competition announcement disseminated through "lunchmeeting"</p>	RCE	21 July 2015	Mailing
<p>Competition announcement</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/libvarna?ref=aymt_homepage_panel</p>	PSRL	Aug 2015	Facebook
<p>My local heritage-invitation to apply Facebook, https://www.facebook.com/Kamra-186973681314259/?fref=ts</p>	Jara	27 Aug 2015	Facebook
<p>Racconta il tuo luogo preferito con le immagini e i documenti online che trovi su #Europeana</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/ranieri.disorbello</p>	FRS	15 Sep 2015	Facebook
<p>Call for entries questionnaire intern (how do people use LoCloud) through intranet</p>	RCE	15 Sep 2015	Mailing
<p>LoCloud competition, National TV station DR2 on their facebook</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/drp2/posts/897491926952724</p>	Via KUAS announcement		Facebook
<p>LoCloud competition, Oplev Halsnæs</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/oplevhalsnaes/posts/721225437981815</p>	Via KUAS announcement		Facebook
<p>LoCloud competition, City archive in Kolding</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/Koldingstadsarkiv/posts/532225576928110</p>	Via KUAS announcement		Facebook
<p>Pronti per il #DigitalHeritage2015</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/ranieri.disorbello</p>	FRS	27 Oct 2015	Facebook

Title, URL	Authors	Date	Place - City, Country (if applicable)	Type
LoCloud Video advertised on ADS website RSS feed and home page.	ADS	25 Mar 2014		
http://www.mecd.gob.es/cultura-mecd/areas-cultura/bibliotecas/mc/concurso-europeana-locloud/inicio.html (Spanish webpage for LoCloud Competition)	MECD	May-Nov 2015	Online	Webpage
http://www.thevillageexpress.com/cyprusvillage/profile/209	Kyperounda Community Council		Kyperounda, Limassol, Cyprus	LoCloud logo
http://www.yeri.org.cy/	Yeri Municipality		Yeri Municipality, Nicosia, Cyprus	LoCloud logo
WIP UDE Website - http://www.wip.wiwi.uni-due.de/forschung/forschungsprojekte/locloud/	UDE			Project description, information, and links